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CLUSTER HEADACHES- A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Cluster headache is a neurological disorder characterized by recurrent, severe headaches on one side of the head, typically around the eye. This condition usually first occurs between 20 and 40 years of age. Men are affected about four times more often than women. Based on the duration cluster headaches can be classified in to acute or episodic cluster headache and chronic cluster headache. The exact cause of cluster headache is unknown. The activation of trigeminovascular, cranial parasympathetic and Internal carotid artery dilation may lead to painful vascular changes within the cavernous sinus, secondary involvement of the sympathetic plexus overlying the cavernous ceratoid artery, and stimulation of secretory function of the lacrimal and other mucosal glands. Common signs and symptoms during a headache include Excruciating pain, generally situated in or around one eye, but may radiate to other areas of your face, head, neck and shoulders ,One-sided pain. Differential diagnosis is necessary. Triptans and supplemental oxygen are first-line abortive therapies for cluster headache. Verapamil and lithium are the mainstays of treatment for chronic cluster headache. Prophylactic therapy is intended to shorten the duration of episodic cluster attacks, in addition to reducing the frequency and severity of attacks in both episodic and chronic cluster headache.

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INTRODUCTION

Cluster headache is a neurological disorder characterized by recurrent, severe headaches on one side of the head, typically around the eye. A cluster headache commonly awakens patient in the middle of the night with intense pain in or around one eye on one side of the head. A cluster headache often accompanied with eye watering, nasal congestion or swelling around the eye, on the affected side. This symptoms typically last for 15 minutes to 3 hours.

Synonyms of cluster headache:

Familial cluster headaches, Histamine cephalalgia, Vasogenic facial pain, Hortons syndrome

EPIDEMIOLOGY:

Cluster headaches probably affects about 1 in 1000 people. It effects 0.1% of the general population at some point in their life and 0.05% in any given year. This condition usually first occurs between 20 and 40 years of age. Men are affected about four times more often than women.their is a lifetime. prevalence of 0.12%

AETIOLOGY:

The exact cause of cluster headache is unknown .But following factors may cause them

Vascular theory:

Cluster headaches were historically called as vascular headaches, with the belief that the intense pain was caused by dilation of blood vessels which in turn, was thought to create pressure on the trigeminal nerve.

Genetics :

People with a first degree relative with the condition are about 14-48 times more likely to develop it themselves and between 1.9 and 20% of persons with cluster headache family history.

Tobacoo smoking:

About 65% of persons with cluster headache are have been tobacoo smokers

Hypothalamus:

A review suggests that the suprachiasmatic nucleus of the hypothalamus, which is the major biological clock in the human body may be involved in cluster headache.

Drugs:

Drugs like nitroglycerin can also cause cluster headaches

RISK FACTORS:

Risk factors for cluster headaches include:

- **Sex:** Men are more likely to have cluster headaches .
- **Age:** Most people who develop cluster headaches are between ages 20 and 50,although the condition can develop at any age.
- **Smoking:** Many people who get cluster headache attacks are smokers. However ,quitting smoking usually has no effects on smoking .
- **Alcohol:** Alcohol can trigger an attack if a person is at a risk of having cluster headache.
- **Family history:** Having a parent or sibling who had had cluster headache might increase the risk

TYPES OF CLUSTER HEADACHES:

Episodic cluster headache:

Episodic cluster headache happens in groups that can last anywhere from 7 days to a year (on average for 6-12 weeks). During each cluster period you may have between one and eight headaches a day. Each one may last from 15 minutes to 3 hours ,although medicines can shorten that time.

Chronic cluster headache:

These are regular headaches that continue for a year or longer .if the patient have any pain free periods, they last for less than a month.

PATHOGENESIS:**Trigeminovascular activation: (CGRP):**

Fig 1: pathogenesis of cluster headaches.

Internal carotid artery dilation (cavernous)

Arterial dilatation and venous outflow obstruction in the region of the cavernous sinus.

The activation of these pathways may lead to painful vascular changes within the cavernous sinus, secondary involvement of the sympathetic plexus overlying the cavernous carotid artery, and stimulation of secretory function of the lacrimal and other mucosal glands.

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS

A cluster headache strikes quickly, usually without warning, although you might first have migraine like nausea and aura. common signs and symptoms during a headache include:

Excruciating pain, generally situated in or around one eye, but may radiate to other areas of your face, head, neck and shoulders , One-sided pain.

- Restlessness
- Excessive tearing
- Redness in your eye on the affected side
- Stuffy or runny nose on the affected side
- Forehead or facial sweating
- Pale skin (pallor) or flushing on your face
- Swelling around your eye on the affected side
- Drooping eyelid

Some migraine like symptoms like sensitivity to light and sound ,can occur with a cluster headache, though usually on one side.

Cluster period characteristics:

- ❖ A cluster period generally lasts from 6-12 weeks.
- ❖ The starting date and the duration of each cluster period might be consistent from period to period. for example, cluster periods can occur seasonally such as every spring or every fall.
- ❖ Most people have episodic cluster headaches. in episodic cluster headaches, the headaches occur for one week to one year, followed by a pain free remission period that can last as long 12 months before another cluster headache develops.
- ❖ Chronic cluster headache periods might continue for more than a year, or pain free periods might last less than one month.

During a cluster period :

- * Headaches usually occurs everyday, sometimes several times a day.
- * A single attack can last from 15 minutes to three hours.
- * These attacks often occur at the same time each day.
- * Most attacks occurs at night, usually one to two hours after you go to bed.

DIAGNOSIS:

Currently there are no diagnostic test to confirm cluster headache.

According to the criteria of the International Classification of Headache Disorders, at least 5 attacks meeting the following are required for diagnosis:

1. severe unilateral, orbital (around the eye)and or temporal (around the temple) pain lasting 15-180 minutes if untreated.
2. headache must be accompanied by at least one of the following:

- * Red eye or tearing on the side of the headache.
- * Nasal congestion or runny nose on the side of the headache.
- * Eyelid swelling on the side of the headache
- * Forehead and facial sweating on the side of the headache
- * Small pupil or eyelid droop on the side of the headache
- * A sense of restlessness or agitation

3. attacks have a frequency from one every other to 8 per day

Differential diagnosis:

Cluster headaches are often misdiagnosed, mismanaged for many years with migraine, tension induced headache.

Fig2:pain associated in different headaches.

TREATMENT:

Treatment for cluster headaches can be categorized in to

- ✓ Episodic cluster headache treatment
- ✓ Chronic cluster headache treatment

TREATMENT FOR EOISODIC OR ACUTE CLUSTER HEADACHE:

Abortive therapy is directed at managing the episodic or acute attacks. Triptans and supplemental oxygen are first-line abortive therapies for cluster headache.

Oxygen

The standard acute treatment of cluster head ache is inhalation of 100% Oxygen via non breather face mask at 12 to 15 liters per minute for 15 to 20 minutes .Repeat administration is necessary in some patient because oxygen merely to delay, rather than abort, the attack in some patients .No side effects have been reported .

Triptans

Sumatriptan given 6mg subcutaneously is considered safe and effective treatment for acute cluster headache .orally administered sumatriptan has limited use in cluster headache because of its relatively long onset of action, adverse effects includes Mild to moderate; rarely lead to discontinuation Injections: dizziness, fatigue, injection site reactions, nausea, paresthesias, vomiting. Zolmitriptan 20-mg nasal spray; maximum of 40 mg per day ,5-mg nasal spray; may be repeated once after two hours, 5 mg orally; maximum of 10 mg per day ,mild adverse effects in approximately 25% to 33% of patients; bad taste, nasal cavity discomfort, somnolence.

Lidocaine

1 mL of 10% solution applied bilaterally with a cotton swab for five minutes. Adverse effects includes Nasal congestion, unpleasant taste.

Octreotide

100 mcg subcutaneously. Adverse effects includes Bloating, diarrhea, dull background headache, injection site reactions, lethargy, nausea.

Ergotamine:

2 mg sublingually, may repeat dose every 30 minutes to a maximum of 6 mg per day. Adverse effects includes Angina, fibrosis (cardiac valvular, retroperitoneal, pleuropulmonary), myocardial infarction, pruritus, vertigo; withdrawal is possible if abruptly stopped.

TREATMENT FOR CHRONIC CLUSTER HEADACHES:

Verapamil and lithium are the mainstays of treatment for chronic cluster headache.

Verapamil

Minimum of 240 mg per day, in single or divided oral doses Adverse effects includes Bradycardia, Constipation, Edema Gastrointestinal discomfort, Gingival Hyperplasia, Hypotension. Electrocardiography should be performed to monitor for heart block

Lithium

800 to 900 mg with meals, in divided oral doses. Adverse effects includes Hypothyroidism, Nephrogenic diabetes Insipidus, Polyuria Tremor

Serum lithium levels should be monitored at least every six months and with dosage changes; thyroid and renal function also should be monitored.

Deep brain Stimulation:

It is a neurosurgical procedure involving the implantation of a medical device called a neurostimulator (sometimes referred to as a 'brain pacemaker'), which sends electrical impulses, through implanted electrodes, to specific targets in the brain (brain nuclei) for the treatment of movement and neuropsychiatric disorders.

Adverse effects includes Micturition syncope, Subcutaneous infection Transient loss of consciousness.

Used only for refractory chronic cluster headache; the effect is not thought to be related to direct hypothalamic stimulation, and failure is not likely caused by electrode misplacement.

PROPYLACTIC THERAPY:

Prophylactic therapy is intended to shorten the duration of episodic cluster attacks, in addition to reducing the frequency and severity of attacks in both episodic and chronic cluster headache .Prophylactic therapies are started early in the cluster period and administered daily until the patient is headache -free for atleast 2 weeks.The medications is then tapered but may be resarted with the next cluster period . Patient with chronic cluster headache may require prophylactic medication indefinitely.

Verapamil

Minimum of 240 to 360mg orally per day, in single or divided doses for episodic attacks, but higher doses may be necessary to control chronic cluster headache.Adverse effects includes Abdominal discomfort, bradycardia constipation edema, gum hyperplasia, hypotension.Electrocardiography required to monitor for prolonged PR interval, change in cardiac axis, or broadening of QRS.

Steroids –

50 to 80 mg of oral prednisone per day, tapered gradually over 10 to 12days, Suboccipital injection: 12.46 mg of betamethasone dipropionate plus 5.26 mg of betamethasone disodium phosphate plus 0.5 mL of lidocaine may be useful for bridging therapy; no adequate randomized controlled trials are available.headaches may recur when therapy is tapered or discontinued. Adverse effects includes hyperglycemia, hypertension, increased appetite, insomnia, nervousness.

Valproic acid

600 to 2,000 mg per day .Adverse effects includes Alopecia, anorexia, dizziness, insomnia, nausea, somnolence, suicidal ideation, thrombocytopenia, weakness, weight gain. Use with caution in patients with renal or hepatic insufficiency; can be used with sumatriptan

Topiramate

25 mg orally for seven days, then increase by 25 mg per day every week to a maximum of 400 mg per day. Adverse effects includes Dizziness, paresthesia, slow speech; mostly well tolerated. Contraindicated in patients with nephrolithiasis.

Ergotamine

3 to 4 mg orally per day in divided doses for up to three weeks; maximum of 6 mg per day or 10 mg per week; give 30 to 60 minutes before anticipated headaches or at bedtime for nocturnal cluster headache. Adverse effects includes Angina, fibrosis (cardiac valvular, retroperitoneal, pleuropulmonary), myocardial infarction, pruritus, vertigo. Contraindicated in patients with peripheral vascular disease, hypertension, or cardiac disease; use with caution in patients with renal or hepatic insufficiency; should not be taken within 24 hours of a triptan; withdrawal is possible if abruptly stopped.

Melatonin

10 mg orally at bedtime and Capsaicin Intranasal application three or four times per day can also be used for preventive therapy.

CONCLUSION

Although cluster headache appears to occur as a results of neuronal dysfunction, the precise etiology and nature of the dysfunction are unknown. A careful patient workup, including patient history, physical examination and appropriate laboratory tests should identify most headache patients with major disease. It is important to identify the cluster headaches with that of migraine,tension type and other headaches as the each type should be treated and monitored differently. Further research need to be done in order to identify and treat cluster headaches appropriately. Patients suffering from cluster headache need to be counselled regularly as they feel socially low because of the pain.so patient counselling and regular follow up will assist the patients with cluster headache to overcome their pain and fear.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that they have no conflicts of interest that are directly relevant to the content.

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